

METHOD FOR DETERMINING ACTIVE POWER LOSSES TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE HYSTERESIS OF THE TRANSFORMER CORE

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Abstract. *The transformer is a converting, transforming and protective device in the power supply system. Active power losses on the transformer core lead to a decrease in the power factor in power supply networks. The article proposes a method for determining active power losses taking into account the dynamic hysteresis loop of the transformer core without additional correction factors over a wide range of frequency changes and the effective value of the network voltage.*

Keywords: *transformer, transformer core, nonlinear inductance, active power losses, correction factor, Weber-Ampere characteristic, dynamic hysteresis loop, equivalent resistance, equivalent capacitance, saturation inductance.*

INTRODUCTION

The transformer is a key device in the power supply system and its efficient operation determines the power factor ($\cos\varphi$) of the network, which depends on the active power losses (P_L) on the core. The lower the P_L , the higher the $\cos\varphi$ and, accordingly, the higher the efficiency (η) in the power supply system.

There are various methods for determining P_L , which provide calculation formulas taking into account the static hysteresis loop of the transformer core with the introduction of additional correction factors when changing the effective value of the network voltage (U). However, in these methods, taking into account the static hysteresis loop of the transformer core requires the introduction of additional correction factors into the formulas for calculating P_L , which affect the accuracy of the calculations. Also, the formulas for determining P_L do not include the influence of an important factor such as a change in the network frequency (f).

The author proposes a method for determining P_L taking into account the dynamic hysteresis loop of the transformer core without introducing additional correction factors and with a wide range of changes in the f and U of the network. Calculation formulas obtained taking into account the dynamic hysteresis loop of the transformer without introducing additional coefficients make it possible to determine the value of P_L with greater accuracy with a wide change in the values of U and f of the network.

RESEARCH METHODS AND THE RECEIVED RESULTS

The study shows that the dynamic properties of the transformer core significantly affect the losses of active power in the saturation mode of the magnetic circuit. As is known, in general, the relationship between the induction and the field strength on the magnetic circuit (core) of the transformer is described by a high-order differential equation [1]:

$$B = \varphi \left(H, \frac{dH}{dt}, \dots, B, \frac{dB}{dt}, \frac{d^2B}{dt^2}, \dots \right) \quad (1)$$

If, as a first approximation, we neglect higher-order derivatives, then the equation takes a simplified form

$$\frac{dB}{dt} - F(H, B) = 0 \quad (2)$$

The analytical expression of equation (2) using the dynamic demagnetization curve (DDC) of the cores is [2]:

$$\frac{dB}{d\tau} = \frac{\mu_e}{\pi} (H - H_c) \quad (3)$$

where, μ_e – equivalent magnetic permeability of the core, determined by the DDC;

H_c – coercive force determined from the static hysteresis loop of the core;

$\tau = \omega t$;

ω - cyclic frequency of core remagnetization.

For the process of remagnetization of the core, equation (3) can be written in the following form [3-4]:

$$\frac{dB}{d\tau} = \frac{\mu_e}{\pi} (H \mp H_c) \quad (4)$$

where the sign “-” corresponds to an increase in the induction in the core, and “+” to its decrease. Taking into account (4), Fig. 1 shows a graphical representation of the approximation of the dynamic hysteresis loop of the core [5-6].

Figure 1. Dynamic hysteresis loop of the transformer core

In practice, expression (1) can be taken as a dependence of current (i) and flux linkage (ψ), which describes the dynamic model of nonlinear inductance (NI) of the transformer (Fig.2) [7-8]:

$$i = F_2\left(\psi, \psi^n; \frac{d\psi}{dt}, \frac{d^2\psi}{dt^2} \dots\right) \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Dynamic model of NI transformer

where, L_s - is the leakage inductance, C_e - is the electromagnetic capacitance, g_e - is the active conductivity, which are equivalent parameters of the NI transformer. $L(i)$ - is the inductance determined by the magnetic permeability of the ferromagnetic material of the transformer core.

Taking into account (5) and considering the constancy of the equivalent parameters for the dynamic model of the NI transformer, we can write [9-13]:

$$i = C_e \frac{d^2\psi}{dt^2} + g_e \frac{d\psi}{dt} + a\psi + b\psi^n + \frac{\psi}{L_s} \quad (6)$$

here, $i_L = a\psi + b\psi^n$ - approximation of the Weber-Ampere characteristic (VAC) of the NI, obtained from the dynamic hysteresis loop $B=f(H)$ of the transformer core.

Taking the voltage $u = U_m \cos \omega t$, flux linkage $\psi = \Psi_m \sin \omega t$ and taking into account the adopted approximation of the VAC characteristic, we obtain

$$i = \left(a - \frac{I_{cm}}{\Psi_m} \right) \psi + b\psi^n \pm \frac{I_{gm}}{\Psi_m} \sqrt{\Psi_m^2 - \psi^2} \quad (7)$$

From the accepted expressions for voltage and flux linkage and taking into account (7), for the instantaneous power of the NI transformer we write [14]:

$$p = ui = U_m I_{lm} \cos \omega t \sin(\omega t + \alpha) - \frac{b}{4} U_m \Psi_m^n \cos \omega t \sin 3\omega t; \quad (8)$$

Then the active power of the NI transformer is determined from the following expression:

$$P = U^2 Y(\omega) \sin \arctg : g_e \left(\frac{a}{\omega} + \frac{3bU_m^2}{4\omega^3} - \omega C_e \right) \quad (9)$$

where, the active equivalent admittance (g_e) is determined from the dynamic coercivity (H_{cd}) of the transformer core. If the induction (B) in the core varies sinusoidally, then H_{cd} is equal to

$$H_{cd} = H_c + 0,125\omega\alpha^2 B_s \sqrt{2\varepsilon - 1} \quad (10)$$

If,

$$Ug_e = \frac{H_{cd}l}{w} \quad (11)$$

and taking into account (10) from (11) we find

$$g_e = l(H_c + 0,125\omega\alpha^2 B_s \sqrt{2\varepsilon - 1}) / \omega w^2 S B_m \quad (12)$$

where, B_s - is the saturation induction, H_c - is the coercive force, d - is the thickness of the magnetic material, ε - is the specific electrical conductivity of the magnetic material, $\sigma = \frac{B_m}{B_s}$ - is the modulation coefficient of the core, w - is the number of winding turns, l - is the average length of the magnetic circuit.

We calculate the equivalent electromagnetic capacitance (C_e) and leakage inductance (L_s) from the condition $\psi = \Psi_r = wSB_r$ and $i = 0$,

$$C_e = \frac{a\psi_r + b\psi_r^n - \omega g_e \sqrt{\Psi_m^2 - \Psi_r^2}}{\omega^2 \Psi_r} \quad (13)$$

$$L_s = \frac{\psi_r}{\frac{1}{\psi_m} (I_{cm}\psi_r + I_{gm}\sqrt{\Psi_m^2 - \Psi_r^2}) - b\psi_r^n} \quad (14)$$

The equivalent nonlinear inductance of the core ($L(i)$) is determined from the condition $\psi = \Psi_m = wSB_m$ and $i = 0$,

$$L(i) = \frac{w\psi_m}{l(a\psi_r + b\psi_r^n)} \quad (15)$$

where, $b = K\omega^3$; $a = \frac{1}{L_s}$ are the approximation coefficients. Taking into account the approximation coefficients and equations (12), (13) and (14), the active power of the NI transformer is determined by equation [15-16]:

$$P = \frac{w^2 S^2 \omega^2 B_m^2}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{\omega L_s} + \frac{3}{2} K U^2 - C_e \omega \right) + g_e^2} \times \sin \arctg g_e : \left(\frac{1}{L_s \omega} + \frac{3}{2} K U^2 - \omega C_e \right) \quad (16)$$

Given that $\frac{1}{L_s \omega} + \frac{3}{2} K U^2 - \omega C_e = 0$ from (13) and (14) we obtain a formula for calculating the active power losses (P_L) on the transformer:

$$P_L = \frac{w^2 S^2 \omega^2 B_m^2}{2} \cdot g_e = 2\pi^2 w^2 S^2 f^2 \sigma B_m^2 = 19,72 w^2 S^2 f^2 \sigma B_m^2 \quad (17)$$

where w – number of winding turns, S – core cross section, f – frequency of the source, σ – specific electrical conductivity, B_m – maximum magnetic induction (approximately equal to the saturation induction (B_s) of the core material).

Given that the flux capacitance $\psi_m = wSB_m$ or $\psi_m = L_s / I_m \sin \omega t$ and accepting $\sin \omega t = const.$, the magnetic induction of the core can be defined as $B_m = L_s w S / I_m$ or $B_m = \omega L_s w S / U_m$. Then, formula (17) has the form:

$$P_L = 19,72 w^2 S^2 f^2 \sigma B_m^2 = 19,72 w^2 S^2 f^2 \sigma / (\omega L_s w S / \sqrt{2} U_{mf})^2 \quad (18)$$

where, the saturation inductance (L_s) of the transformer is defined by the equation

$$L_s = 1,3 \pi w/4 * d^2 / a * K_a \mu_0 \quad (19)$$

where w - number of turns in the primary winding, d - thickness of magnetic material, a - average winding height, K_a - winding shape factor, μ_0 - relative magnetic permeability of air.

Expressions (17) and (18) have a high enough accuracy in comparison with known formulas for calculating active power losses (P_L) in transformers, and also allow to determine losses in NI without additional correction factors in a wide range of frequency changes (f) and effective voltage values (U).

CALCULATION METHOD

Here is the method for calculating the active power losses (PL), taking into account the following reference and calculation parameters of the electromagnetic voltage transformer windings – ZNOL.6/0.4-24UZ:

Table 1.

Transformer brand	$S_{nom.}$ [kVA]	Catalog data						Calculation data	
		$U_{nom.}$ [kV] – windings		U_{κ} [%]	ΔP_{κ} [kW]	P_x [kW]	I_x [%]	R_T [Ohm]	X_T [Ohm]
		HV	LV						
ZNOL. 6/0.4-24UZ	6,0/0,4	6,0	0,4	1,385	1,25	0,125	2,6	4,7	14,5
Geometric and magnetic data									
w – number of turns in the primary winding	d_a [mm] – average diameter of the primary winding	d_o [mm] – outer diameter of the primary winding	a [mm] – average winding height	K_a – winding shape factor	μ_0 [Gn/m] relative magnetic permeability of air				
2175	115	190	96	0,5815	$4\pi * 10^{-7}$				

Maximum magnetic induction - $B_m = B_s = 1,5 Tl$;

Source voltage frequency - $f = 50 Hz$;

Specific conductivity of copper - $\sigma = 55,55 * 10^{-6} Sm/m$.

Transformer no-load current $I_x = 0,26 A$;

Rated transformer phase voltage - $U_{nf} = 1386 V$

Core cross section - $S = (d_o - d_a) * a = (190 - 115) * 96 = 7,2 * 10^3 mm^2$;

According to equation (19) the transformer saturation inductance $L_s = 5,423 Gn$.

Considering that changes in frequency and supply voltage actively affect the NI of the transformer, it is relevant to calculate the active power losses, taking into account the variation of these values.

Calculation of active power losses (P_L) by formula (17) with frequency change (f) and unchanged voltage (U_{nf}) (Table 1.).

Calculation of active power losses (P_L) by formula (18) at changing voltage (U_{nf}) and constant frequency (f) (Table 1.).

Table 2.

$U_{nf} = 1386 V = const. \quad f = var.$										
f (Hz)	50	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	<i>Then linear increase P_n</i>
P_n (kW)	15,1	30,2	35,4	42,7	60,9	91,1	131,2	170,3	192,7	
$f = 50 Hz = const. \quad U_{nf} = var.$										
U_{nf} (V)	400	800	1200	1600	2000	2400	<i>Then linear increase P_n</i>			
P_n (kW)	6,2	11,4	28,8	32	38,4	44,8				

Below are the calculated characteristics of the active power losses (P_L) of a ZNOL.06-24UZ transformer from the nominal phase voltage (U_{nf}) and frequency (f) (Fig.3 a and b). It can be seen from the characteristics that a change in frequency (f) significantly increases the active power loss (P_L) than a change in the nominal phase voltage (U_{nf}) of the transformer.

Figure.3. Calculated characteristics of active power losses ($P_n = P_L$) transformer ZNOL.06-24UZ

CONCLUSION

1. The proposed method for calculating active power losses (P_n) in transformers has a fairly high accuracy compared to known calculation formulas.
2. The calculation method allows determining active power losses (P_n) in transformers without additional correction factors in a wide range of frequency (f) and voltage (U_{nf}) changes.
3. Changing the frequency (f) and rated phase voltage (U_{nf}) almost linearly increases the active power losses (P_n) of the transformer (Fig. 3 a and b), which negatively affects the quality indicators of power supply.

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